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The Magic of Reading

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In a cozy corner, books in a pile,
A teacher's smile, full of style.
Little ones gather, eager and bright,
Ready to learn, in the morning's light.

She opens a book, pages unfold,
Stories of heroes, brave and bold.
Words come alive, letters like friends,
In tales that twist, and turn, and bend.

She points to words, and letters so neat,
The sounds they make, are so sweet and fleet.
With a patient voice, she sounds them out,
Her love for reading, is beyond any doubt.

They trace each letter, write their name,
Learning letters, a joyful game.
The alphabet dance, a magical show,
In every child's heart, love does grow.

Through ups and downs, they journey on,
From simple words to tales of the dawn.
They read aloud, their voices clear,
Each word is a gem, each line so dear.

In her hands, books become a key,
To worlds unknown, for all to see.
Imagination soars, minds ignite,
In the world of reading, pure delight.

In her care, they learn to read,
A skill to cherish, a skill they need.
With books in hand, they take their flight,
In stories old and stories bright.

Oh, the magic she weaves, through every page,
In the hearts of children, at every stage.
With books and dreams, she makes a start,
Guiding them with love, in reading's art.

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